

A Study of Relationship between Teaching Aptitude and Work Motivation of Secondary School Teachers

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Abstract

The purpose of the present study is to measure the relationship between teaching aptitude & work motivation of secondary school teachers of district Saharanpur. This is a survey study under descriptive research. For the present study, random sampling technique has been used for collecting the sample for the present study. 8 colleges were selected randomly on the bases of lottery system and a total of 50 teachers regardless of their gender have been taken as sample for the study. For the collection of data the researcher administrated the Teaching aptitude test battery by Dr. R.P. Singh & Dr .S.N. Sharma & Work motivation questionnaire by K.G .Aggarwal. After collection of data relationship between teaching aptitude and work motivation of secondary school teachers has been sought with the help of product moment coefficient of correlation and the results were analyzed and interpretation were drawn. The results obtained were checked at both the levels of significance i.e. at 0.01 and 0.05. It was observed from the findings that there was no significant relationship between teaching aptitude and its components and work motivation of secondary school teachers.

Keywords: Teaching Aptitude, Work Motivation, Secondary school teachers.

Introduction

Teaching is the process of changing the behavior and developing desirable skills in learner for his all round development. The process of teaching to be conducted effectively depends upon effective teachers. No development of new technology can revolutionize the classroom teaching unless capable and committed teachers are there in teaching profession. The success of a teacher depends on his self-control, good teaching aptitude and work oriented mind. Singh (2015) believed that no nation can rise above the level of its teachers and it is the teacher who plays pivotal role in the educational system and is a catalytic agent of change in the society. A teacher should not only be competent in his subject, teaching methods, understanding the learner but also has a favorable aptitude towards teaching profession. It is well said that if aptitude refers to "quality of being fit for a purpose or position", then teaching aptitude is the quality of being fit for teaching profession. That is why, it is considered as the introductory determinant factor of effective teaching. Dictionary in English (2011) enumerated that teaching aptitude means probability of success in teaching. Whereas, Kumar (2012) considered the teaching aptitude means an interest in the teaching work orientation, implementing teaching principles and methods. Kaur (2014) described teaching aptitude as a specific capacity or special ability, distinct from the general intellectual ability of an individual, indicative of his probable success in a particular field after receiving appropriate opportunity for learning or training. A constructivist teacher's role is to foster and direct his work on the part of students. A teacher with teaching aptitude encourages students to use active techniques to create more knowledge and then to reflect on and talk about what they are doing and how their understandings are changing. Research indicates that everyone does not have the ability or the aptitude to take up teaching. Certain minimum

requirements in the way of intelligence, temperament, and personality are observed to be highly critical. Hence, teaching aptitude is considered as the determinant factor for choosing the teaching profession. When we say a person possesses an aptitude for teaching, it is assumed that he has a good proportion of the traits required for becoming successful in teaching.

According to Bingham :- As a condition symptomatic in his readiness to acquire proficiency his potential ability and another is this readiness to development an interest in exercising his ability. The five dimensions of teaching aptitude are following:

1. Mental Ability
2. Attitude Towards Children
3. Adaptability
4. Professional Information
5. Interest In Profession

Work motivation is a set of active forces that originate within and beyond an individual's being, to initiate work-related behavior and to determine its form, direction, intensity and duration. Motivation can be used as a tool to help predict behavior; it varies from person to person and sometimes combined with ability and environmental factors to improve the behavior as well as performance. Work motivation helps a person to increase his performance level and willingness towards a task. It is important for any organizations to understand and to create a healthy work environment to encourage productive and enthusiastic behaviors. It can be done with the help of right motivation strategies. Three psychological processes are concerned with work motivation: arousal, direction, and intensity. Arousal is provocation, which is stimulated by individual's necessities. Direction is the way; a person follows in achieving the aims. Intensity is the amount of energy an individual put into task performance. Motivation can help the employees to focus on particular task. It encourages them to put best of their abilities. Motivation prevent one from deviating from the goal-seeking behavior and results in task strategies.

According to Mitchell & Daniels (2003), define it as- patterns of behavior produced to reach a particular goal, in their study measurement in universities-implications for work motivation revealed that performance measurement is based on quantitative rather than qualitative measures. The current management by results system has a negative effect on work motivation. In the light of the findings of the study it revealed that management by results is in conflict with intrinsic motivation.

Significance of the Study:

As a teacher, Teaching Aptitude is the force that facilitates excellence in a learner. A teacher's poor aptitude in teaching can be detrimental for the learners. In order to teach the teacher must possess aptitude to teach the student. The professional preparation of teachers and aptitude towards teaching has been recognized to be crucial for the qualitative improvement of education since the 1960s. Present study have practical implications for secondary school teachers. Both teaching aptitude and work motivation plays very important role in teachers' s educational development because it gives the opportunity to know oneself and to know others. The role of the study shows that extensive training and consistent support are necessary to enhance work motivation and the programs like seminar, workshop etc. should be organized to help the teachers to improve teaching aptitude. The present study shows that teaching aptitude can develop new skills and knowledge among the teachers. Also, it would be helpful to know student's contribution for society, contribution of society and duties of individual towards the society. The present study is intended to find the teaching aptitude and work motivation of teachers. The manuscript in hand is beneficial not only for Present time but also provide a base for future educational development of secondary schools teachers.

Statement of The Problem:

"A Study of Relationship between Teaching Aptitude and Work Motivation of Secondary School Teachers"

Objectives:

To study the teaching aptitude of secondary school teachers.

- 1) To find out the relationship between teaching aptitude and work motivation of secondary school teachers.
- 2) To find out the relationship between mental ability component of teaching aptitude and work motivation of secondary school teachers .
- 3) To find out the relationship between attitude towards children component of teaching aptitude and work motivation of secondary school teachers.
- 4) To find out the relationship adaptability component of teaching aptitude and work motivation of secondary school teachers.
- 5) To find out the relationship between professional information component of teaching aptitude and work motivation of secondary school teachers.
- 6) To find out the relationship between interest in profession component of teaching aptitude and work motivation of secondary school teachers.

Hypotheses:

- There is no significant relationship between teaching aptitude and work motivation of secondary school teachers.
- There is no significant relationship between mental ability component of teaching aptitude and work motivation of secondary school teachers.
- There is no significant relationship between attitude towards children component of teaching aptitude and work motivation of secondary school teachers .
- There is no significant relationship between adaptability component of teaching aptitude and work motivation of secondary school teachers.
- There is no significant relationship between professional information component of teaching aptitude and work motivation of secondary school teachers.
- There is no significant relationship between interest in profession component of teaching aptitude and work motivation of secondary school teachers.

Delimitations:

1. The study comprised the Sample of 50 Secondary school teachers regardless of their gender.
2. The sample was limited to secondary school teachers of U.P. Board .
3. The Present study has been confined to Secondary Schools only where the medium of instruction is Hindi.
4. The Present Study has been confined to Secondary School Teachers of Saharanpur District .

Methodology:

The descriptive survey research method has been applied in the study.

Population and Sample:

The population of the present study teachers teaching at secondary level have been considered regardless of their gender. Thus, the result of the present study will only be applicable to this population of secondary school teachers. For the present study, random sampling technique has been used for collecting the sample for the present study. 8 colleges were selected randomly on the bases of lottery system and a total of 50 teachers regardless of their gender have been taken as sample for the study.

Variables Involved:

Independent Variable : Teaching Aptitude

Dependent Variable : Work Motivation

Tools

1. Teaching aptitude test battery by Dr. R.P.Singh & Dr .S.N. Sharma.
2. Work motivation questionnaire by K.G Aggarwal

Statistical Techniques:

Product moment co-efficient of correlation has been used to measure the relationship between Teaching Aptitude and Work Motivation.

Data Analysis and Interpretation:

To test the relationship between the two variables of the study Pearson's Product Moment correlation technique was applied. Significance of correlation coefficient was checked afterwards to test the significance of the hypotheses. The results obtained are mentioned in the table given below.

TABLE

	Relationship between variables	r- value	Level of significance
1.	Teaching Aptitude and Work Motivation	- 0.0234	NS
2.	Mental Ability component of Teaching Aptitude and Work Motivation	- 0.0349	NS
3.	Attitude Towards Children component of Teaching Aptitude and work motivation	- 0.1655	NS
4.	Adaptability component of Teaching Aptitude and Work Motivation	+ 0.0524	NS
5.	Professional Information component of Teaching Aptitude and Work Motivation	- 0.6128	Significant at 0.01 level
6.	Interest In Profession component of Teaching Aptitude and Work Motivation	+ 0.41	Significant at 0.01 level

Findings:

The first hypothesis of the study was there is no significant relationship between teaching aptitude and work motivation of secondary school teachers. Obtained r value is zero point -0.0234. Thus there is negative but negligible relationship between both the variables. While considering the critical value of r it was found that obtained r value is not significant at both the levels of confidence hence it may be interpreted that no significant relationship exist between teaching aptitude and work motivation of the teachers teaching at secondary level of education. Thus null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between teaching aptitude and work motivation of secondary school teachers is accepted.

The second hypothesis of the study was there is no significant relationship between mental ability component of teaching aptitude and work motivation of secondary school teachers. Obtained r value is -0.0349. While considering the critical value of r it was found that obtained r value is not significant at both the levels of confidence hence it may be interpreted that no significant relationship exist between mental ability of teaching aptitude and work motivation of the teachers teaching at secondary level of education. Thus null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between mental ability of teaching aptitude and work motivation of secondary school teachers is accepted.

The third hypothesis of the study was that there is no significant relationship between attitude towards children component of teaching aptitude and work motivation of secondary school teachers. Obtained r value is zero point -0.1655. While considering the critical value of r it was found that obtained r value is not significant at both the levels of confidence hence it may be interpreted that no significant relationship exist between attitude towards children component of teaching aptitude and work motivation of the teachers teaching at secondary level of education. Thus null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between attitude towards children component of teaching aptitude and work motivation of secondary school teachers is accepted.

The fourth hypothesis of the study was that there is no significant relationship between adaptability component of teaching aptitude and work motivation of secondary school teachers. Obtained r value is $+0.0524$. While considering the critical value of r it was found that obtained r value is not significant at both the levels of confidence hence it may be interpreted that no significant relationship exist between adaptability component of teaching aptitude and work motivation of the teachers teaching at secondary level of education . Thus null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between adaptability component of teaching aptitude and work motivation of secondary school teachers is accepted.

The fifth hypothesis of the study was that there is no significant relationship between professional information component of teaching aptitude and work motivation of secondary school teachers. Obtained r value is zero point -0.6128 . Thus there is negative but moderate relationship between both the variables. While considering the critical value of ' r ' it was found that obtained ' r ' value is significant at 0.01 level of confidence hence it may be interpreted that significant relationship exist between Professional Information component of teaching aptitude and Work Motivation of secondary school teachers. Thus null hypothesis that there is significant relationship between Professional Information component of teaching aptitude and Work Motivation of secondary school teachers is rejected. Negative Sign shows that Professional Information component of Teaching Aptitude and Work Motivation of secondary school teachers have negative correlation. It may further be interpreted that with the increase in professional information, work motivation of teachers decreases and vice versa.

The sixth and last hypothesis of the study was that there is no significant relationship between interest in profession component of teaching aptitude and work motivation of secondary school teachers. Obtained r value is zero point $+0.41$. Thus there is positive but low relationship between both the variables. While considering the critical value of ' r ' it was found that obtained ' r ' value is significant at 0.01 level of confidence hence it may be interpreted that significant relationship exist between Interest In Profession component of teaching aptitude and Work Motivation of secondary school teachers. Thus null hypothesis that there is significant relationship between Interest In Profession component of teaching aptitude and Work Motivation of secondary school teachers is rejected. Positive Sign shows that Interest In Profession component of Teaching Aptitude and Work Motivation of secondary school teachers have positive correlation. i.e. if teachers have interest in teaching profession their work motivation also increases accordingly.

Conclusion:

In this study we find the relationship between teaching aptitude and work motivation based upon the correlation coefficients presented through the table. On the basis of findings of the study it may be concluded that teaching aptitude along with its components has negative correlation with work motivation, although the magnitude of relationship is very low or almost negligible.

Implication of the Findings:

The findings of the study have practical implications for secondary school teachers.

Present study owes the following educational Implications:-

1. The findings of the study have practical implications for secondary school teachers.
2. Present study also helps teachers to know the teaching aptitude and work motivation of secondary school teachers.
3. Both teaching aptitude and work motivation plays very important role in teacher's educational development because it gives the opportunity to know oneself and to know others.
4. The present study would enhance teacher's learning and helps to maintain coordination between classroom management and society.
5. The present study will help the secondary school teachers to come out of their introvert behavior. It would help them to have believe in themselves.

6. The present study shows that extensive training and consistent support are necessary to enhance work motivation and the programs like seminar, workshop etc. should be organized to help the teachers to improve teaching aptitude.
7. The present study shows that teaching aptitude can develop new skills and knowledge among the teachers. Also, it would be helpful to know student's contribution for society, contribution of society and duties of individual towards the society.
8. The present study is intended to find the teaching aptitude and work motivation of teachers.

Therefore, the present research is beneficial not only for Present time but also provide a base for future educational development of secondary schools teachers.

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